

The food fraud landscape: A brief review on food safety and authenticity

Leonidas Sotirios Kyrgiakos¹, Malak Hazimeh², Marios Vasileiou¹, Christina Kleisiari¹, Georgios Kleftodimos² and George Vlontzos¹

¹ Department of Agriculture Crop Production and Rural Environment, University of Thessaly, Fytoko, 38446, Volos, Greece; lkyrgiakos@uth.gr; mariosvasileiou@uth.gr; chkleisiari@uth.gr; gvlontzos@uth.gr

² Mediterranean Agronomic Institute of Montpellier (CIHEAM-IAMM), University of Montpellier, Montpellier, France; malakhzm24@gmail.com; kleftodimos@iamm.fr

Abstract

Food fraud poses a significant challenge within the global food supply chain, with apprehensions regarding safety, authenticity, and efficiency. This study conducts a brief review of the literature by utilizing the Web of Science database, analyzing 2,331 outcomes pertaining to the subject of food fraud. The analysis results demonstrated a noteworthy surge in scientific publications after 2013, which was propelled by events such as the horsemeat scandal and the formation of the European Food Safety Authority. Utilizing Multiple Correspondence Analysis (MCA), the study identified significant clusters pertaining to food transformation, safety, traceability, and distinct meat sources. In addition, trending topics shifted towards a holistic approach to food safety and the implementation of technologies like Blockchain (BC), Internet of Things (IoT), Artificial Intelligence (AI), and Big Data (BD). These technologies offer enhanced traceability, authentication, automation, and decision-making capabilities. The present research offers valuable perspectives on the evolving landscape of food fraud research and the potential of nascent technologies to tackle these issues.

Keywords: Food fraud; food safety; food authenticity; food supply chain; review; industry 4.0; sustainability; blockchain; food traceability; Multiple Correspondence Analysis (MCA)

Acknowledgment: *This research has received funding from the European Union's HE research and innovation pro-gramme under grant agreement No 101084188. Views and opinions expressed are, however, those of the author only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for any use that may be made of the information the document contains.*